

IMPROVING REAL ESTATE MANAGEMENT WITH MODERN TECHNOLOGIES

Berdibayeva Guliza Berdibay qizi

Tashkent University of Architecture and Civil Engineering, doctoral student

bbguliza@gmail.com

Annotation

This publication provides an overview of the best practices and technologies in real estate management. Their comparative analysis is carried out, assessing the strengths and weaknesses of different strategies. Special place is given to the study of the growing concept of sharing and its current implementations in international real estate. The contrasts between established rental practices and innovative models such as Rent-to-Own, QuintoAndar and fintech tools are analysed. In addition, it highlights the activities of companies that are actively implementing digital solutions to ensure greater transparency and convenience when making transactions.

Keywords: real estate market; rental property; lease agreement; tenant; lessor; sharing economy; co-consumption economy; digitization; online platforms; Airbnb; short-term rental; long-term rental; Rent-to-Own; Divvy Homes; Home Partners; QuintoAndar; fintech; financial technologies; Jetty.com; digital services; cybersecurity; real estate investments; affordable housing; housing programs; mortgage rates; small-sized housing; urban infrastructure; socio-economic model; legal responsibility; Equality of the parties; transparency of transactions; modernization of housing construction; innovative approaches; flexible rental arrangements; transformation of the real estate market.

ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ НЕДВИЖИМОСТЬЮ С ПОМОЩЬЮ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ

Аннотация

В настоящей публикации представлен обзор передовых методов и технологий в сфере управления недвижимостью. Проводится их сравнительный анализ с оценкой достоинств и уязвимостей различных стратегий. Особое место занимает исследование набирающей обороты концепции шеринга и её актуальных воплощений на международной арене недвижимости. Анализируются контрасты между устоявшимися арендными практиками и инновационными моделями, такими как Rent-to-Own, QuintoAndar и финтех-инструменты. Кроме того, освещается деятельность компаний, активно внедряющих цифровые решения для обеспечения большей прозрачности и комфорта при совершении сделок.

Ключевые слова: рынок недвижимости; аренда недвижимости; договор аренды; арендатор; арендодатель; sharing economy; экономика совместного потребления; цифровизация; онлайн-платформы; Airbnb; краткосрочная аренда; долгосрочная аренда; Rent-to-Own; Divvy Homes; Home Partners; QuintoAndar; финтех; финансовые технологии; Jetty.com; цифровые сервисы; кибербезопасность; инвестиции в недвижимость; доступное жильё; жилищные программы; ипотечные ставки; малогабаритное жильё; инфраструктура городов; социально-экономическая модель; юридическая ответственность; равноправие сторон; прозрачность сделок; модернизация жилищного строительства; инновационные подходы; гибкие условия аренды; трансформация рынка недвижимости.

Introduction

The relevance of the study is determined by the volatility of the real estate market, where long-term forecasts are limited, but analysis of current trends allows to identify directions of its development [1]. Leasing as a form of property relationship involves the temporary transfer of ownership to the lessee for a fee [2]. In the last 15 years, the rental sector has undergone significant changes due to the spread of sharing economy (CME) technologies that have transformed the classic ownership model into an access model [3]. An example of such changes has been the short-term rental platforms, including Airbnb,

that have influenced the development of hybrid forms and the combination of leasing with a mortgage [4].

The concept of the sharing economy is based on the principle of temporary access to resources, which has proved to be more convenient and economically justified for broad segments of the population [5]. According to experts, the share of the co-consumption economy will increase from 5% to 30% by 2025 [6]. The real estate market is central: according to analysts, the volume of transactions based on sharings has exceeded \$15 billion and is projected at \$335 billion by 2025 [7]. An important trend is the digitalization of rental processes, which allows owners to determine market rates more effectively, conduct tenant audits and use new financial instruments. In turn, tenants have access to simplified and transparent transactions. Thus, modern platforms are shaping new standards of service quality and convenience.

Methodology

The study applied a method of comparative analysis, which made it possible to compare different rental models and identify their strengths and weaknesses. For this purpose, scientific publications, official statistics and case studies were studied, including the experiences of the USA, Brazil, Europe and CIS countries. The work used methods of systematization and content analysis, which made it possible to highlight key trends such as leasing fintecs, the Rent-to-Own model and digitalization through platforms like QuintoAndar. The qualitative analysis of cases was also applied, which made it possible to evaluate both successful examples and challenges of introducing new technologies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The housing problem in Uzbekistan occupies a central place among socio-economic issues, since it is related to traditions, culture and infrastructural constraints [8]. Similar challenges are also characteristic of other CIS countries, including Russia, where government programs to provide affordable housing are implemented [9]. At the end of 2021, about 15% of Russians rented a home, equivalent to more than 21 million people

[10][11]. The increase in rental transactions is due to higher mortgage rates, which has made rent more attractive [12].

According to M.E. Nepomnyashey, the share of tenants in the Russian Federation increased from 8% in 2018 to 15% in 2021, and further growth is forecast [13]. In the works of J. V. Chugunov emphasis is placed on the need to improve organizational and legal forms of financing and construction of small-sized housing [14]. Studies by Uzbek authors highlight the importance of increasing the volume of housing construction and modernization of urban infrastructure [15]. Thus, analysis of the literature confirms that rent is becoming an increasingly important form of housing provision.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The rental market is a system of transactions based on contractual relationships between lessors and lessees [16]. The basic principles include equality of the parties, return of the object at the end of the contract and legal responsibility of the participants. The current market is characterized by several key trends.

The first is financial technology development on a long-term lease. Services such as Jetty.com solve the problem of deposits and first payments by offering flexible rental terms and credit to tenants. Fintec increases the availability of transactions, speeds up transactions, reduces costs and provides real-time access to data [17]. However, there are shortcomings: threats to cybersecurity, lack of personalization, regulatory constraints [18].

The second trend is rent with subsequent buyback (Rent-to-Own). It allows the tenants to test the object before buying and if necessary, cancel the transaction. Such models are widely used in the US and Europe by Divvy Homes and Home Partners, offering alternatives to classic mortgages [19].

The third example of innovation is the platform QuintoAndar (Brazil), which has fully digitalized the rental process. Service eliminates the need for guarantors and deposits, guarantees payments and covers repair costs. Transaction time has been reduced to 1.5

hours, and the rate of contract renewals exceeds 90%. As of 2021, the company reached an estimate of \$4 billion [20].

In this way, modern forms of leasing, including financial solutions, Rent-to-Own and digital platforms, are transforming the market by making it more flexible and technological. In doing so, they create new opportunities for tenants and owners, but at the same time raise issues of regulation and cybersecurity.

CONCLUSIONS AND PROPOSALS

Digitization and new business models in the rental industry make it more profitable and convenient for both owners and tenants. Modern technologies allow to optimize processes and reduce costs. They also provide transparency in transactions, making rental agreements easier to manage and reducing the risks of fraud. In addition, the introduction of digital tools enables real-time access to property data, which enhances decision-making for both landlords and tenants. The use of automation and data analytics has also made it possible to predict demand, set dynamic pricing, and improve the overall efficiency of property management.

This approach has been successfully applied in the US, Europe, Brazil, and Russia, where governments and private companies have invested heavily in digital platforms and services. For example, in Brazil, the company QuintoAndar has revolutionized long-term rental agreements by eliminating excessive bureaucracy and providing reliable guarantees for both sides. Similarly, in the US, fintech solutions such as Jetty.com have simplified financial procedures for tenants by offering flexible deposit and insurance schemes. These examples show that digital transformation in the rental industry is not limited to one region but represents a global trend. At the same time, the sharing economy model continues to grow, changing the very concept of property ownership and promoting more flexible living arrangements.

Its further development depends on improved legislation and innovative solutions. Governments must ensure clear regulatory frameworks that protect both tenants and

landlords while fostering technological innovation. Stronger collaboration between public institutions and private companies is also necessary to implement sustainable practices and enhance social responsibility in the housing sector. Moreover, advances in artificial intelligence and blockchain are expected to further transform property management in the coming years. By integrating these technologies, the rental industry can increase trust, reduce transaction times, and open new opportunities for investment. Ultimately, the combination of digitization, innovation, and legal adaptation will determine the long-term stability and growth of this sector.

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